

ΕΛ.Ι.Ν.Τ.

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THE BIO-CONTENT OF THE DISTILLATE MARINE FUEL IS NOT THE ONLY RESPONSIBLE FACTOR FOR THE MICROBIOLOGICAL GROWTH

- S. Kalligeros, Fuels & Lubricants Laboratory, Hellenic Naval Academy, End of Hadjikyriakou Avenue, 18539 Piraeus, Athens Greece, e-mail: sskalligeros@hna.gr
- P. Adonakos, Fuels & Lubricants Laboratory, Hellenic Naval Academy, End of Hadjikyriakou Avenue, 18539 Piraeus, Athens Greece, e-mail: pan.adonakos@hna.gr

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ABSTRACT

Microbes are present everywhere, usually microbes being carried into fuel tanks either by the entrance of water or by air. Therefore, the microbial contamination of the marine fuels has been recognized as a severe problem for over the last 50 years. The microbiological growth will occur when the microbes come into contact with the free water, otherwise they are remaining dormant. The present study took place in one of the largest world hovercrafts with NATO reporting name “Pomornik” class which has the Russian designation project “1232.2” also known as “Zubr”. The ship has a standard full load displacement of 555 tons, its landing craft has a cargo area of 400 square meters and a fuel capacity of 56 tons. The vessel has a cruising speed of between 50 - 60 knots (25.7 to 30.8 m/s). Other characteristics of the ship is that it has three 4-bladed ducted propellers with diameter approximately 5.2 m (17 ft) in order to supply lift four fans were used. The axial-flow fans type was used, same as the most of the Pomornik's predecessors, the Gus, the Lebed and the Aist hovercraft. In this study, the microbial contamination influenced by corrosion of metal alloys without exposure to alternative fuels including FAME (biodiesel), was examined.

KEY WORDS

Microbiological Growth, Microbiological Contamination (MBC), Distillate Marine Fuel (DMF), Filter Blocking, Fuel Deterioration

1. BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

The navies around the world have experienced a steady increase in the contamination of fuels by the existence of microbes (UK Defence Standard 2020). There are many reasons for this phenomenon including the insulation provided by double bottoms. In many fuel systems the water compensation found that has contributed to the microbiological growth. The microbes needing the elements of carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus to build their cell structure (In-Sik 2004). They use the water as the life passage of nutrients and other materials across their cell wall. The Microbiological Contamination (MBC) of the fuel has deleterious effects (Haggett et al. 1993). These effects are (Haggett et al. 1993, Lee et al. 2010, Little et al. 2008):

- fuel filter blocking,
- fuel injectors damage,
- pumps damage,
- turbine blade corrosion,
- turbine blade erosion,
- fuel line clogging and

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- fuel deterioration.

The fuel filter blocking can be occurred both with dead and live microbiological origin biomass. The presence of the water is essential for the establishment of microorganisms, but their food is the fresh fuel. Additionally, the biocides can also feed the MBC, and this is one of the reasons why the biocides used infrequently. There are also serious problems that can be caused by staff exposure to the biocides. In the first stage of MBC, aerobic microbes grow at the interface between fuel and water. In practice, unless there is meticulous management of the fuel there is always the possibility that there is water in the fuel tanks even from the condensation of any moisture. Regular fuel recirculation would greatly assist in the conversion of a potential Microbial Contamination into large-scale parasitism.

In case a large Microbial Contamination has developed at the fuel / water interface then a membrane is created which in turn prevents oxygen from being transported further into the water. This, combined with the bacteria's need for oxygen, removes oxygen from the water. This oxygen-depleted environment is ideal for anaerobic bacteria to grow. These bacteria are called Sulphate Reducing Bacteria (SRB). It is a group of anaerobic bacteria that thrive in these conditions and feed on the sulfur compounds of the fuel, but also on the organic alcohols, and the acids produced by the degradation of the fuel. This class of bacteria cannot tolerate the presence of either molecular or dissolved oxygen. Sulfates in seawater are converted by bacteria in this category to corrosive sulfides. Part of them is used as "food" (nutrient) for the further growth of SRB bacteria, but most of them are filtered in the tank environment and cause corrosion. These sulfide ions are extremely corrosive to tank materials by creating craters (pitting) leaving sulfur ions in them. A number of classes of SRB bacteria produce sulfuric acid which is extremely corrosive. In all cases the prevention of microbial infection is the best method. Regular removal of fuel from tanks and filtration using a suitable filter and centrifuge separator helps to control Microbiological Contamination (Frederick 2003). While generally high temperatures accelerate the growth of microbiological infection, rinsing the tanks with water at prolonged temperatures above 60 ° C kills the majority of the microbes that make up the MBC.

The primary factors influencing microbial growth are:

- the air (oxygen availability),
- the water,
- temperature,
- acidity (pH),
- the availability of nutrients,
- the osmotic pressure and
- the salinity.

The aerobic microbes require oxygen to be active (typically > 5mg/lt). The anaerobic microbes are active only in an oxygen-free environment (usually <2 mg/L). Potential anaerobic germs can thrive in a well-ventilated and anoxic environment. Potential anaerobic microbes play a critical role in ecological fuel systems. This is because they sweep oxygen and create anoxic conditions, favorable exclusively for anaerobic media, such as biological membranes, sludge, sediments, but also other cavities where fuel and water can remain stagnant within the fuel transport and storage systems.

The germs do not need free water. Instead, they require water to be available, as measured by water activity. Water activity is defined as the ratio of the pressure of water vapor over a material to the

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pressure of water vapor over pure water (Scott, 1957). The best-known bacteria will not thrive at water activity lower than 0.95, but few of them will thrive when the water activity will be around ≈ 0.75 . Enough fungi grow in environments where the water activity is equal to 0.60. The aqueous phase does not need to be large in volume to support microbial growth. It is the surface area of the fuel/water interface, which is perhaps most important in determining the degree of microbial multiplication. Hydrocarbon nutrient levels will be particularly high in the immediate vicinity of this interaction surface. The oxygen concentration will also be relatively high, and the fuel itself will contain a certain amount of dissolved oxygen (Hill, Evans, & Davies, 1967).

Up to a certain critical temperature, the growth rate and the increase in metabolism increase with the temperature increment. This relationship is linear - logarithmic. As the temperature increases linearly, the activity increases logarithmically. Above the critical temperature, others call it “the optimal temperature”, the rates of the growth rate and the increase of microbial metabolism, fall sharply. Although for each type of microbe there is a characteristic optimal growth curve in combination with temperature, and relative humidity, there are three general trends shown in Figure 1. From the graphic expression it is understood that the prolonged storage of fuel in the tanks of the ship (in case of long immobility), in which seawater has entered, in combination with the parking of the ship on the landing slopes (greater exposure to high summer temperatures than if it was in the sea), allow the development of high temperatures during the summer months inside the tank, a factor that dramatically affects the growth and spread of microbial contamination in the stored fuel.

The acidity measurements at both bottom and runoff waters inside the fuel systems, differ significantly and consequently the characterization of alkalinity or acidity. This reflects the chemistry of the water-soluble components of the fuel at the top of the tanks and fuel systems, the origin of the water, and the biodegradable processes that take place within the fuel supply system. Most germs prefer a pH ranging from 6 - 8.5. Fungi, however, tend to prefer an environment with a lower pH than bacteria and germs. The greatest diversity of fungi is found in environments with a pH ranging from 4.5 to 6.5.

Figure 1. Effect of the Temperature on the Growth of Microbes.

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Fuel is a hostile environment for most germs. Only germs in the initial phase which are at the same time inactive are capable of long-term viability in the fuel layer. Most bacteria in the fuel do not reproduce and therefore die quickly, often within days or even hours, unless contained in water droplets (Hill, Evans, & Davies, 1967) (Hedrick & Crum, 1968). At the fuel-water separation surface, they can survive indefinitely (Bento & Gaylarde, 2001) (Hill & Thomas, 1976). It should not be forgotten that contamination of the fuel by dead germs can also cause operational problems such as clogging of the filter. This very non-survival of several microbes in the fuel phase also has consequences for the validity of test results when there is a delay between fuel sampling and testing to find viable microorganisms (egg colony or formation unit). Tests for viable germs that are performed more than a few days after taking the fuel samples may significantly underestimate the contamination or not even detect it. The vast majority of germs will normally be detected in the water phase at the bottom of the fuel tank or system. The membranes (biofilm) that adhere to the inner surfaces of the tank may contain even higher numbers of germs. These, however, are generally inaccessible and extremely difficult to sample. All of these adversities make sampling and analysis finding microorganisms an extremely complex process. This is the reason, why there must be always a visual view of the tank and knowledge of the fuel system. This explains why negative results in the examination of the samples can be occurred.

In the present study we have examined the MBC in one of the largest operational hovercraft ships with NATO reporting name “Pomornik” class which has the Russian designation project “1232.2” also known as “Zubr”.

2. DISCUSSION

During a mission trip the recorded problem was the filter plugging, resulting in insufficient fuel supply, as provided by the manufacturer's operating parameters. The result was an unruly ship. The visual inspections of the filters are depicted in Figure 2. On the other hand, a new clear filter has the appearance of Figure 3.

Figure 2. The plugged filters.

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Figure 3. New fuel filter.

Distillate Marine Fuel Samples received from the oil tank of the ship and from the bunkering vessel fuel supply line. The samples were analyzed in an accredited laboratory and the results illustrated below between figures 4 - 7, shows the distillation curves for both samples.

Figures 4, 5 and 6 it is understood that the samples are identical in terms of their hydrocarbon composition and basic physicochemical properties, because the analytical characteristics of the examined properties are identical.

However, examining the samples for their content of Metals, specifically Calcium, the sum of Sodium plus Potassium, Lead and Vanadium, it was noticed that there is a significant difference in the diesel fuel sample of the ship's tank. The results of the measurements are presented in Figure 7. The increased content of Sodium, Potassium, Lead and Vanadium can create problems with deposits in the fuel system and attack the metals of the combustion chamber but this only in cases that are outside the specifications. In this particular case, their concentration is within the specifications, but the existence of corrosion inside the ship's fuel tanks was need further investigation. The samples were also examined in a special laboratory for the possible existence of microbes and fungi in them and the result was negative. However, this result does not comply with Figure 2, for this reason it was decided to conduct a visual inspection inside the tanks of the ship.

Based on the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) standard AFLP-7063 the treatment in order to decontaminate the product and the equipment either can involve the use of fuel biocide additive or elimination of the fuel and cleaning the equipment. The principles of a curative treatment are summarized as follows:

- Drain the aqueous phase,
- Incorporate a biocide at the recommended dosage,
- Homogenate the fuel,
- Fuel decantation at the recommended duration and
- Draining and Filtration

The use of a biocide must consider that it has no harmful effect, at the recommended concentrations, on navy engines, turbines, turbines engines and equipment. The usage of biocide must follow the recommendations of the proper authority. The use of biocide as a regular fuel additive is prohibited. The reason is because of the frequent use of the biocide at a sublethal level may lead to the development of resistance mechanisms from micro-organisms which can degrade its efficiency.

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Table 1 illustrates the biocidal additives for the navy fuels which were use from the NATO nations (NATO 2015). The higher dosage which is acceptable for use usually is a shock dosage in case of an extremely high contamination and only used once after the cleaning process if the biocontamination is still present.

Figure 4. Distillation curves of the samples.

Figure 5. Density, Residues + Losses, Kinematic Viscosity and Sulfur concentration.

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Table 1. NATO nations use of biocides.

Nation	Product Name	Dosage	Decantation Time (Hours)	Higher dosage (acceptable for use)
Belgium	S-1751	100 ppm vol.	48	100 ppm vol.
Bulgaria	-	-	-	-
Canada	-	-	-	-
Czech Republic	-	-	-	-
Germany	GrotaMar 82	1000 ppm vol.	72	
Denmark	BIOBOR JF	270 ppm vol.	36	270 ppm vol.
Spain	BIOBOR JF BUSAN	150 ppm vol. 5ppm vol.	100 100	-
Estonia	-	-	-	-
France	RS-1754 RS-1753	200 ppm vol. 1kg/50t	24 24	400 ppm vol. 2kg/50t
Great Britain	-	-	-	-
Greece	-	-	-	-
Hungary	-	-	-	-
Italy	-	-	-	-
Lithuania	-	-	-	-
Luxemburg	-	-	-	-
Latvia	-	-	-	-
Nederland	NETBIOKEM SP 15	50 ppm vol.	48	500 ppm vol.
Norway	MAR 71	1000 ppm vol.	48	300 ppm vol.
Poland				
Portugal	MAR 71	200 ppm vol.	48	200 ppm vol.
Romania	-	-	-	-
Slovakia	-	-	-	-
Slovenia	-	-	-	-
Turkey	-	-	-	-
United States of America	Biobor JF	110 ppm vol.	n/a	110 ppm vol.

During the period of cleaning and repairing the fuel tanks of the ship, it was possible to have a visual inspection of the tanks before and after cleaning. Tank No. 3 was initially examined as shown in Figure 8. The black surfaces and spots on the tank give the impression that there is fungal growth which can cause microbial contamination of the fuel. For this reason, the inspection of the remaining tanks (1, 2, 4, 5, 6) of the vessel was also took place. Their status is illustrated in Figures 9 to 13, respectively. The development of a dark layer in the storage tanks were observed, which appeared to be more concentrated on surfaces where there was a liquid level. However, in order for the microbial contamination to develop, water must be present. In order to do this, in addition to the fuel water, there must also be an inflow of water into the tanks. To determine if this is the case the condition of No. 3 tank was captured after it had been cleaned with hot water at 60°C and repairs had been conducted.

Figure 14 shows the fuel suction point in the tank and the filling (filling) of material to correct the corrosion is evident. This point was probably a point from which there was an inflow of sea water

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into the tank. It is also pointed out the existence of black spots which in all probability are a source for maintaining the fungi in the Tank.

The metal thickness in this area was recorded at 4.7 mm (ultrasonic measurement). Figure 15 shows two parts of the tank with intense corrosion which have not been repaired at this stage and are possible points of water inflow in the future. The thickness of the tank bottom at these points was measured to be 4.3 mm. Various entrance points were repaired during the mentioned repair period. It should be emphasized that it would be desirable to process the points of these tanks in accordance with the standing orders and instructions of the Hellenic Navy.

Figures 6. Cold Flow Properties.

It is necessary after any repair of the interior of the tanks in which microbial contamination has occurred, that there are no cavities which can be points of "capture" of the fungi. This is because these points in turn will be the foci of infection.

3. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the problem presented by analyzing the clogging of the fuel filters in a "Pomornik" (Zubr) class hovercraft. It should be mentioned that it was not possible to sample the colloidal film that appeared on the oil filters. From the aforementioned and what has been cited, it is estimated that the clogging of the filters was the result of microbial contamination, which comes from the inflow of seawater into the fuel tanks.

The development of Microbial Contamination (MBC) is due to the fact that fuel is food for microorganisms. Microorganisms do not grow in the fuel but at the water-fuel interface, which is why the oil samples did not show any microbial contamination. In addition, the storage conditions of the fuel for a lengthy period of time in the ship's tanks are considered unsafe for the quality of the fuel, in terms of possible microbial contamination, for the following reasons:

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- possible inflow of sea water,
- lengthy periods of time where the fuel remains stagnant,
- exposure of the tanks to the high temperatures of the summer months.

Figure 7. Metals Concentration.

Figure 8. View of Tank No. 3 before cleaning. Possible fungal colonies which have developed mainly on the bottom of the tank. In several regions, the spread of infection occurs.

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Figure 9. View of Tank No. 1 before cleaning. Possible fungal colonies which have developed mainly on the bottom of the tank. No spread of the infection occurs in the regions.

To treat it the following recommendations have been made:

- Repair the corrosion of the tanks which are water inflow centers. An immediate check of the oil tanks after each voyage is recommended.
- Clean the tanks with prolonged use of hot water above 60 °C.
- The use of microbicides is considered pointless.
- Any handling of the fuel prior to its storage in the vessel's tank is pointless without any benefit.
- Instead, the fuel, in order to avoid maximizing the problem, should be cleaned after shipping the boat by recirculation using a centrifuge and a simple particle retention filter. By using the centrifuge, the water is removed and by using the filter, the population of microbes is minimized.
- It is advisable to keep the fuel tanks empty and clean when the ship remains stationary for a lengthy period of time, especially during the summer months.

After following the above recommendations, the problem has disappeared from these ships.

Figure 10. View of Tank No. 2 before cleaning. Possible fungal colonies which have developed mainly on the bottom of the tank. Colonies have started to spread in the reservoir areas. Also, it can be seen that the fungi are concentrated at the level of the liquid.

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Figure 11. View of Tank No. 4 before cleaning. Possible fungal colonies which have developed mainly on the bottom of the tank. Colonies have started to spread in the reservoir areas. Also, it can be seen that the fungi are concentrated at the level of the liquid.

Figure 12. View of Tank No. 5 before cleaning. Possible fungal colonies which have developed mainly on the bottom of the tank. In this tank there is extensive spread of colonies.

Figure 13. View of Tank No. 6 before cleaning. Substantial fungal colonies which have developed mainly on the bottom of the tank. In this tank there is extensive spread of colonies.

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Figure 14. View of Fuel Suction Point (inside & outside). The thickness at the repaired point is measured at 4.7 mm.

Figure 15. Corrosion Points which have not been repaired. This point is measured at 4.3 mm thickness.

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